

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D.4.1 – REINFORCING Platform

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the current status of the development of the REINFORCING website/platform in month nine.

As it is exposed in the text, the current status of the platform is a project website with basic information about the project, its activities and its ambitions. The look & feel of the website is not finished yet and it will be completely refurbished during the next month. In the meantime, potential ORRI grantees and actors interested in REINFORCING resources can have access to the REINFORCING platform whilst this redesign is happening.

The REINFORCING platform will have two more releases, in month 18 and in month 48, where different features will be added such as information about the funding cascade mechanism and REINFORCING open calls, project news, project reports and ORRI tools among others.

1. REINFORCING PLATFORM

The release of the REINFORCING platform in month nine aims to set up a project website for the REINFORCING project. Under Task 4.1, REINFORCING platform aims to be “*the European entry-point to ORRI expertise, services, experiences, tools, resources and practices for users from all types of institutions and quadruple helix sectors.*” (REINFORCING GA, page 11).

To this aim the setting up of the REINFORCING virtual platform is a mandatory step to become this reference for the European research and innovation community. REINFORCING virtual platform will have three releases. A first one, with a basic website in month 9, a second one incorporating the new taxonomy produced by WP1 in month 18, and a last one in month 48 including new resources from grantees and funded projects.

REINFORCING platform will also “inherit” the RRI tools list of resources and these materials will be re-structured according to the new taxonomy to be developed in WP1. The REINFORCING platform aims to leverage the last three decades of open and responsible research and innovation in the Union and to be collected into a singular point of access available for all stakeholders interested on it.

In addition, the current release of the REINFORCING platform is also incorporating a map (see figure 1) of ORRI ambassadors and ORRI facilitators. The objective of this virtual map is to gather information from ORRI ambassadors and ORRI facilitators (more details below), so as to provide them with visibility toward potential ORRI newcomers interested in both learning from their experience and asking for their support in the implementation of ORRI processes and to joining forces for the application to the REINFORCING open calls.

REINFORCING
Responsible Research and Innovation Models and Culture Scan
Research and Innovation Resources for Sustainable Development

Home News Ambassadors / Facilitators

Ambassadors / Facilitators

1. What is an ORRI Facilitator and an ORRI Ambassador?

An ORRI facilitator is an entity with strong experience in supporting and facilitating ORRI institutional changes.
An ORRI ambassador is an entity which have hands-on experiences of ORRI implementation in their own institution and territory.

2. Join the ORRI Facilitators and Ambassadors Map!

Why joining?

- Showcase your ORRI experience in the REINFORCING map
- Possibility of being contacted by actors interested in ORRI
- More visibility for becoming a potential partner in projects funded by REINFORCING

3. Want to be part of the REINFORCING ORRI Map?

If you are motivated to be listed in the ORRI Map, please register your entity through this form:

Institution

City

Figure 1 ORRI Ambassadors/Facilitators register

1.1 Technical specifications

As it is stated in the REINFORCING GA, the REINFORCING platform has been set up with Free Libre Open Source (FLOSS) technologies. The content management system chosen for the implementation of the platform has been Headless Wordpress which is a version of

the most popular software used for websites that allow to connect Application Programming Interfaces (APIS) and associated databases. The portal has been developed by REACT technical framework which allows to develop the front-end and the back-end of the portal at the same time. Wordpress is compatible with standards such as HTML5, CSS3 and dynamic languages such as AJAX, and Javascript. The platform is hosted by TECNALIA web servers and managed through dedicated hosting services.

1.2 Basic structure

This first release of the REINFORCING platform is composed by a basic structure of the platform which is focused on providing a basic project website structure. To this aim the website provides information about project consortium, ORRI grants, ORRI Map. This basic structure will gain in complexity through the following months due to the ORRI platform/One-stop source development.

Figure 2 About page

Grants

Grants

REINFORCING project will provide financial support to third parties in the form of grants.

All REINFORCING calls will adhere to EU principles of transparency, equal treatment, conflict of interest, and confidentiality, ensuring an objective and clear selection procedure.

Two kinds of grants will be delivered by REINFORCING:

- **ORRI booster** → small grants of 20K EUR
- **ORRI incubator** → large grants of 60K EUR

7 calls will be launched throughout the 50 months of REINFORCING: 4 Booster calls and 3 Incubator calls

Small grants, also called ORRI boosters, will be awarded to applicants (at least one beneficiary) already experienced in ORRI which would like to strengthen and institutionalize their ORRI approach. Each ORRI booster call will support 12 organizations implementing an 8-month project.

Large grants, also called ORRI incubators, will be awarded to consortia of beneficiaries (at least two beneficiaries per consortium) that are newcomers in ORRI and would like to embark on an ORRI approach. Each ORRI incubator call will support 8 consortia implementing a 12-month project.

More info will be released for each launch with details and guidelines for applicants in advance.

Figure 3 ORRI grants

1.3 ORRI Ambassadors & Facilitators

In addition, the current release of the REINFORCING platform is also incorporating a map of ORRI ambassadors and ORRI facilitators. The objective of this virtual map is to gather information from ORRI ambassadors (entities which have hands-on experiences of ORRI implementation in their own institution and territory) and ORRI facilitators (entities with strong experience in supporting and facilitating ORRI institutional changes). The objective of this map is to help potential ORRI applicants to connect with EU experts, matching their needs for specific skills or expertise by potential ORRI proposals.

Figure 4 ORRI country map

1.4 Next steps

Before the implementation of the full One-Stop Source, the website will be revamped with catchy graphics – aligned with the project visual identity – and more sections will be inserted. Here following a tentative list of sections of the website main menu:

- About
 - o Consortium
 - o Advisory Board
 - o Project plan
 - o Methodology
- Grants
 - o Open Calls
 - o FAQ and Guidelines
 - o Evaluators
- ORRI Map
- News
- Project Resources
 - o Deliverables
 - o Publications and Reports

Changes and revisions could occur.